

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the present study entitled “**CORRELATION OF ENDOMETRIAL VASCULARITY WITH IMPLANTATION AMONG SUBFERTILE WOMEN**” has been undertaken by Dr. Jeena Baaniya, a student of MD in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology of Tribhuvan University Teaching Hospital, Kathmandu under our direct supervision and guidance. The data incorporated in this thesis are original and have been verified by us.

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that I am the sole author of the present study relating to the thesis entitled “CORRELATION OF ENDOMETRIAL VASCULARITY WITH IMPLANTATION AMONG SUBFERTILE WOMEN” conducted at Tribhuvan University Teaching Hospital, Maharajgunj, Kathmandu, Nepal and that it has not been submitted to any other paper or publications.

I also hereby authorize the Tribhuvan University to use or replicate this thesis in any form for academic benefits.

Dr. Jeena Baaniya

DEDICATED

TO

MY FAMILY

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I would like to take this opportunity to express my gratitude towards everyone who have contributed from his/her standpoint to make the completion and writing up of this thesis possible.

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Dr Jeena Baaniya

ABSTRACT

Objective: To correlate preovulatory endometrial vascularity with conception

Study design: Hospital based prospective descriptive study

Study period: One year i.e. 1st Jestha 2072 1st Jestha 2073 (15th May 2015- 14th May 2016)

Methodology: All the couples i.e. 1130 women attending Infertility Clinic were taken for study. History was taken, examination was done and investigations were sent. Women who fulfilled inclusion criterias were taken for the statistical analysis after excluding male factor, tubal factor, endocrinological factor, ovarian factor and uterine factor of subfertility. Ovulation and induction was done with 50mg of Clomiphene citrate for 5 days from day 2 to day 6 of cycle and follicle monitoring was done 9th day onwards along with endometrial thickness and endometrial vascularity according to Applebaum's four zones of endometrial vascularity till development of adequate size follicle or day 20 of cycle. Intra muscular beta human chorionic gonadotropin was given and luteinizing hormone surge test was done. Women who were LH surge positive were then regarded as case and those women who failed to develop adequate size follicle, those women who were LH surge negative were excluded. Women either opted for intrauterine insemination or natural conception and urine pregnancy test was done 21 days later in these women and those who tested positive were confirmed by transvaginal sonogram after three to four weeks.

Results: 1130 women were enrolled for the study but only 81 women were taken for the analysis as remaining 1049 women were lost to various factor during study period.

Majority of the women i.e. 46.9% in the study belonged to the age group of 26 to 30 years. The mean age was 27 years while the mean age in women who became pregnant was 24 years. 71% in the study population had primary subfertility and remaining 9% had secondary subfertility. 67% of women who became pregnant had primary subfertility while remaining 33% had secondary subfertility. 61% of women had normal body mass index and 67% of women who became pregnant had normal BMI. The mean BMI was 23.21 +/- 3.61 kg/m². The correlation between pregnancy and BMI was not statistically significant.

The mean endometrial thickness in the study population was 7.9mm while it was 7.8mm in women who became pregnant. 84% of women had endometrial thickness between 6-14 mm and 95.3% of implantation was seen in the same group but the correlation between implantation and endometrial thickness was not statistically significant. 47% of women had zone III endometrial vascularity and maximum number of implantation was seen in this zone accounting for 67% of implantation while zone I endometrial vascularity had no implantation though the correlation between endometrial vascularity and pregnancy was not statistically not significant. The correlation between endometrial thickness, endometrial vascularity and pregnancy showed low degree of negative correlation in this study population.

Conclusion: Though the correlation between pregnancy with endometrial thickness and endometrial vascularity were statistically not significant, majority of pregnancy was seen in the group of zone III endometrial vascularity and in the group with endometrial thickness of 6 to 14mm than in other groups.

Keywords: endometrial vascularity, endometrial thickness, pregnancy

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ABBREVIATIONS

BMI	Body Mass Index
EMT	Endometrial Thickness
ET	Embryo Transfer
EV	Endometrial Vascularity
FET	Frozen Embryo Transfer
FSH	Follicle Stimulating Hormone
LH	Luteinizing Hormone
GnRH	Gonadotropin Releasing Hormone
GOPD	Gynecology Out Patient Department
hCG	Human Chorionic Gonadotropin
HSG	Hysterosalpingogram
IOM	Institute of Medicine
IUI	Intrauterine Insemination
IVF	Invitro Fertilization
OCP	Oral Combined Contraceptive Pill
SD	Standard Deviation
TFT	Thyroid Function Test
TUTH	Tribhuvan University Teaching Hospital

TVS	Transvaginal Sonogram
USG	Ultrasonography
WHO	World Health Organization
3D	Three Dimensional
4D	Four Dimensional
ed.	Edition
i.e.	That is
mm	millimeter
MHZ	Megahertz
yrs	Years

1 INTRODUCTION

Infertility is the inability to conceive regardless of cause after a period of one year of unprotected intercourse of reasonable frequency.¹ It can also be defined as a disease of the reproductive system defined by the failure to achieve a clinical pregnancy after 12 months or more of regular unprotected sexual intercourse.² Fifteen percent of couples worldwide experience either primary or secondary infertility.² It can be subdivided into primary infertility that is with no prior pregnancies and secondary infertility, which refers to infertility following at least one prior conception. Infertility is not only a medical problem, but has also often social and psychological implications.

Successful pregnancy requires a complex sequence that includes ovulation, ovum pick-up by a fallopian tube, fertilization, transport of a fertilized ovum into the uterus, and implantation into a receptive uterine cavity and development. In the male system, sperm of adequate number and quality must be deposited at the cervix near the time of ovulation.³

In couples attempting conception, 57 percent of women become pregnant at 3 months, 72 percent become pregnant at 6 months, and 85 percent become pregnant by 1 year and 93 percent become pregnant by 2 years.⁴

Infertility can be caused by female and/or male factors. It can be attributed to the female partner one third of the time, the male partner one third of the time, and both partners in the remaining one third.³ In females, ovulatory dysfunction accounts for 40% of cases

while tubal and pelvic pathology accounts for 40% and remaining 20% is attributed to unexplained and unusual factors.³

Endometrial receptivity is significantly affected by the blood supply to the endometrium. Uterus is supplied by both the uterine artery derived from internal iliac artery and the ovarian artery derived directly from aorta which anastomoses with one another. The blood supply of the endometrium comes from the circumferentially oriented arcuate arteries of the myometrium derived from uterine artery. The branches from these arteries pass to the endometrium as radial arteries and they form the straight or basal arteries which supply the stratum basalis and the coiled or spiral arteries which supply the stratum functionalis. The straight arteries do not undergo cyclic changes and the constant blood supply to the stratum basalis contributes to its stability. Before the onset of menstruation the spiral arteries constrict causing ischemia and shedding of the stratum functionalis with loss of progesterone support.

Angiogenesis plays a critical role in various female reproductive processes such as development of a dominant follicle, formation of a corpus luteum, growth and receptivity of endometrium, implantation and development of the placenta.

For a very short time during the menstrual cycle, the endometrium allows for the implantation of gestational sac and this feature is referred to as endometrial receptivity. A good blood supply of the endometrium is considered as an essential requirement for implantation and can be assessed by ultrasound using various parameters including endometrial vascularity.⁵

Recently, there have been reports about the role of optimum endometrial conditions in predicting pregnancy outcome. Hence it's possible that blood flow in the peri-implantation endometrium may have effect on success or failure of conception.⁶

Vaginal sonography is an effective method for evaluating uterine and ovarian changes. Recently particular attention has been focused upon the value of endometrial sonography indices for predicting success rate of reproductive programs.^{7, 8} An appropriate endometrium is one of the major factors in success of embryo implantation and failure may be due to insufficient endometrial circulation.^{9, 10}

Studies based on Doppler sonography have revealed considerable difference in pattern of endometrial circulation alteration during days of natural menstrual cycle.

The role of endometrial vascularity in implantation has been a controversial topic with some studies showing positive correlation and some showing no role.

One of the method of evaluation of endometrial receptivity is Applebaum's zones of vascularity for categorizing endometrial vascularity. According to Applebaum endometrial vascularity is divided into four zones. The zones of vascularity are defined as zone I if vascularity in color Doppler is seen only at endometrium myometrium junction, zone II when vessels penetrate through the hyperechogenic endometrial edge, zone III when vessels reach intervening hypoechogenic zone and zone IV when vessels reach the endometrial cavity.¹¹

Figure 1: Periovulatory triple lined endometrium

Figure 2: Zone I Endometrial Vascularity

Figure 3: Zone II Endometrial Vascularity

Figure 4: Zone III Endometrial Vascularity

Figure 5: Zone IV Endometrial Vascularity

This study intends to correlate the role of endometrial vascularity in implantation in Infertility Clinic of Tribhuvan University Teaching Hospital. The role of endometrial vascularity in implantation is a controversial topic with some studies showing positive correlation and some showing no role. This study is first of its kind to be performed in our setting.

Hence this study would help to determine if endometrial vascularity could be used as a predictor of implantation and to apply the result in patient with poor endometrial vascularity for prescribing vascularity increasing agents.

2 OBJECTIVES

2.1 General Objective

1. To correlate preovulatory endometrial vascularity with conception.

2.2 Specific Objective

1. To compare the different zones of vascularity with implantation.
2. To assess the conception rate in relation to the endometrial vascularity in different zones i.e.
 - a. Zone I
 - b. Zone II
 - c. Zone III
 - d. Zone IV

3 LITERATURE REVIEW

Infertility is the inability to conceive regardless of cause after a period of one year of unprotected intercourse of reasonable frequency.¹ Fifteen percent couples worldwide experience either primary or secondary infertility.² It can be subdivided into primary infertility that is with no prior pregnancies and secondary infertility, refers to infertility following at least one prior conception.

Female fertility is regulated by a complex coordination and synchronization of interactions in the hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian axis. Female fertility can thus be influenced by different diseases or dysfunctions of reproductive tract, neuroendocrine system, and immune system or by any general disease.

Wide spectrum of factors affect conception, implantation and endometrium plays a vital role in the establishment of normal pregnancy. Identification of markers of endometrial receptivity would allow better understanding of functional endometrium. Specific endometrial development during the luteal phase of menstrual cycle is vital for successful pregnancy.⁷

Endometrium is a complex organ that assumes various essential roles for successful pregnancy. It proliferates during follicular phase of menstrual cycle followed by timely secretory changes in luteal phase with stromal decidualisation ready to sustain pregnancy.⁸ These changes are influenced by hormonal environment.⁹ Therefore the most favorable approach in improving implantation is predicting the time of optimal endometrial receptivity which does not have accepted criteria but is only assessed circumstantially.

The tubal factor of infertility can be diagnosed in many cases by hysterosalpingography, saline sonography or laproscopic chromotubation while ovarian factor can be detected by transvaginal sonography, hormone profile, but there is not any exact method to determine the endometrial receptivity. However transvaginal sonography can measure the endometrial thickness, determine the type of endometrium and the grade of endometrial vascularity. Hence the quantification of uterine blood flow may play an important role in prediction of implantation rate.

3.1 ENDOMETRIUM

The endometrium is regarded as an endocrine organ, producing several hormones, growth factors and cytokines. The main function of the endometrium is to allow a timely implantation of a viable embryo, and to provide a nurturing local environment that supports establishment of a successful pregnancy. Endometrial functions include the ability to trigger its own destruction in the absence of pregnancy, and protection against invading pathogens.¹²

A narrow portion of the endometrium adjacent to the myometrium is not shed at menstruation and is called the stratum basalis and the cells from the glandular epithelium, stroma and blood vessels of this stratum basalis proliferate and restore the endometrium after menstruation. The more superficial and thicker layer of the endometrium, which is formed after menstruation, is called the stratum functionalis. This layer is highly sensitive and responsive to oestrogen, progesterone and androgens and is subsequently discharged during menstruation.¹³ This layer has a cycle of proliferation, secretion and degeneration. The purpose of the functional layer is to prepare the endometrium for embryo implantation.

The endometrium can be divided into two hormone responding tissue types i.e. single layer of columnar epithelium, and stromal connective tissue, that contains fibroblasts, endothelial cells and leukocytes.¹⁴ The types of epithelium in the endometrium are luminal epithelium (covers the endometrial surface) and glandular epithelium (lining of glands). Luminal epithelium provides the sites of implantation, as it is the first maternal surface for the trophoblast cells of the implanting embryo to encounter.¹⁵ In addition, luminal epithelium acts as a blood, uterine lumen barrier, which prevents substances to enter the uterus from the blood .¹⁶ Glandular epithelial cells secrete several autocrine and paracrine factors required for endometrial maturation and embryo implantation. Fibroblasts are the dominant cell type of the stroma, and produce extracellular matrix, metalloproteinases and other proteins .¹⁴ Stromal endothelial cells locate in the wall of arteries and veins, and are essential for the formation of new vessels from the existing ones, i.e. angiogenesis.

Angiogenesis plays a critical role in various female reproductive processes such as development of a dominant follicle, formation of a corpus luteum, growth of endometrium, implantation and development of the placenta.^{17, 18, 19}

Implantation is a phenomenon that involves a cascade of events between the embryo and maternal endometrium. In a menstrual cycle there is a brief and specific time period in which the maternal embryonic interaction is optimal and culminates with adhesion and invasion of the blastocyst into the progesterone induced secretory endometrium. This period is referred to as the “nidation window” or “implantation window”. The implantation window is characterised by changes in the endometrial epithelial morphology marked by the appearance of membrane projection called pinopodes.

Pinopodes are progesterone dependent organelles that look like apical protrusion appearing in between day 20 & 21 of a 28 days cycle.

Figure 6: Electron microscopic picture of preovulatory endometrium

Implantation in human is a complex process that involves embryo apposition and attachment to maternal endometrial epithelium, traversing adjacent cells of epithelium and invasion into the endometrial stroma.

If for any reason, synchronization between the blastocyst and endometrium fails, implantation does not occur or embryo is aborted. In the absence of implantation second set of changes commences that ultimately leads to menstruation. The molecular process that occur between the implanting conceptus and the endometrium involves intra cellular and cellular to extra cellular matrix interactions, mediated by lectins, intergins, matrix degrading enzymes and their inhibitors, prostaglandins, variety of growth factors, cytokines and angiogenetic peptides.

For a very short time during the menstrual cycle, the endometrium allows for the implantation of gestational sac and this feature is referred to as endometrial receptivity. Recently, there have been reports about the optimum of these endometrial conditions in predicting pregnancy outcome. Currently scientific understanding of a receptive and

non-receptive endometrium is incomplete. Consequently, there is no single definitive investigative marker for adequacy of an endometrium for implantation.

Endometrial receptivity is being evaluated by a large variety of parameters with varying sensitivity and specificity. These include serum biochemical markers which reflect molecules that are induced or are present in receptive endometrium. The assessment using tissue samples for conventional microscopy, histochemistry, electron microscopy and of late, newer ultrasound imaging techniques. It is possible that blood flow in the peri-implantation endometrium may have effect on success or failure of conception. Successful implantation depends on a close interaction between the blastocyst and the receptive endometrium. Ultrasound examination of the endometrium allows a noninvasive evaluation of endometrial receptivity. The different ultrasound parameters have been used in the evaluation. Currently available ultrasound techniques of evaluation for endometrial receptivity include gray scale sonography using high frequency transvaginal scans, conventional color Doppler studies, power Doppler, three dimensional (3D) and real time three and four (4D) dimensional studies and tomographic ultrasound imaging.

The parameters that have been studied over the past to decades, more so the last few years, include endometrial thickness, endometrial volume, endometrial ultrasound morphology, subendometrial peristalsis, endometrial and subendometrial vascularity, myometrial echogenicity, myometrial power Doppler, spectral analysis of uterine artery flow velocity waveforms and perifollicular vascularity.

3.2 HORMONAL REGULATION OF ENDOMETRIAL CYCLE

The menstrual cycle consists of a follicular phase (menstruation and proliferative phase) and a luteal or secretory phase, separated by ovulation. A normal cycle has approximately the same length in each time, from 21 to 35 days with an average of 28 days. The series of classic morphological changes in the endometrium occur in response to cyclical ovarian activity.²⁰

Ovarian function is under the control of luteinising hormone and follicle stimulating hormone, which bind to their receptors in the ovary and regulate its function by promoting sex steroid production and folliculogenesis²¹.

The hypothalamus secretes pulses of GnRH, which regulates the pituitary gland to produce gonadotrophins in a pulsatile pattern. When gonadotrophins act on the follicles, the production of oestrogens increases and reaches its maximal level in the preovulatory follicle. Estradiol is the main estrogen synthesised and has dual action in gonadotrophin secretion, at low circulating levels it exerts negative feedback control over FSH and LH production by inhibiting GnRH secretion, meanwhile at high circulating levels positive feedback becomes a dominant force and LH and FSH surge is induced, followed by the ovulation. Ovarian follicular phase coincides with the endometrial proliferative phase. Growing levels of estradiol exert mitogenic effects on the endometrium, leading to cell division and growth of the endometrium and angiogenesis.¹⁴

After ovulation, the oocyte moves along the fallopian tube for potential fertilization and the dominant post-ovulatory follicle transforms into corpus luteum. LH promotes luteinisation of mature follicles and maintains progesterone production from the corpus luteum. High levels of progesterone, in the presence of estrogen, form a negative feedback action that suppresses gonadotrophin secretion. This coincides with the start

of the endometrial secretory phase. Progesterone is the main hormone that regulates the endometrial maturation for blastocyst implantation. The progesterone dominated latter half of the menstrual cycle is constituted by an early, mid and late secretory phase. Implantation takes place during the mid-secretory phase. The pattern of sex steroid receptor expression in the secretory endometrium reflects the fact that the early secretory phase is regulated by both estrogen and progesterone; the midsecretory phase is regulated by progesterone alone and the late secretory phase is associated with progesterone withdrawal and consequently menstruation.²² The histological features characteristic for the receptive endometrium are increased glandular volume, secretion, edema, coiling of spiral arteries and decidualisation of the stroma.²³ In the absence of pregnancy, corpus luteum degenerates, resulting in decrease of circulating steroids, that lead to enhanced secretion of FSH and the initiation of a new cycle.²⁴

3.3 ASSESSMENT OF ENDOMETRIAL RECEPTIVITY

3.3.1 Transvaginal Sonography

Transvaginal sonography has significantly steered infertility management and has extended the scope of gynecology. It is an essential tool in modern infertility management. The vaginal transducers enables noninvasive and detailed monitoring of growing follicles, visualization of ovarian, uterine and endometrial morphology. The changes in the endometrial thickness and pattern has been analysed in spontaneous and ovarian induced cycles.²⁵ However precise relationship with endometrial thickness, its pattern and vascularity with TVS has not been elucidated.

A good blood supply of the endometrium is considered as an essential requirement for implantation and is assessed by ultrasound.

From the first day of the menstrual cycle until the mid-cycle, the normal endometrium progressively thickens and develops sonographically detectable strata. This appearance can be described as layered, trilaminar. Past the mid-cycle, the normal endometrium brightens and progressively becomes thin.²⁵ These sonographic endometrial patterns appear to be related to the changes in the glandular and vascular elements of the endometrium during the menstrual cycle.^{26, 27, 28}

Fleischer et al determined that the endometrium is thickest during the secretory phase (3.6 +/- 1.4 mm), less thick during the proliferative phase (2.9 +/- 1.0 mm) and thinnest during menstruation.^{27, 28} These values are for the half-thickness as measured from the endometrial canal to the endometrial-myometrial junction. Full thickness measurements ranged from 4 to 12mm, with an average thickness of 7.5 mm. The endometrium will either slough if no pregnancy occurs or will undergo various changes in the event of a pregnancy.

As an implantation marker, endometrial thickness is characterized by its significant sensitivity (95-100%), but also shows a high number of false positives (78-97%)²⁹ therefore, the main advantage is a high negative predictive value (87-100%). The main advantage of measuring endometrial thickness lies in its high negative predictive value in cases where there is minimal endometrial thickness.²⁹

In IVF cycles it was reported that a minimal endometrial thickness of 7 mm to be accepted as a reliable sign of sub-optimal implantation potential.³⁰ Although it is possible to achieve pregnancies with a thin endometrium^{31, 32}, this is always a bad predictive factor that requires further study of the endometrium.³³ It has also been

reported that implantation, pregnancy and miscarriage rates are negatively affected by the endometrium being thicker than 14mm^{31, 33, 34, 35} although data from other studies do not support this finding.^{36, 37, 38}

There is a positive correlation between increased endometrial thickness and pregnancy rates and further explained that this effect is dependent on the age of the patient, duration of stimulation, and embryo quality.^{38, 39} Contrary to these data, other studies showed that measurement of endometrial thickness had no predictive value for pregnancy in ART.^{40, 41, 42, 43, 44}

Freidler et al. reviewed 2665 assisted conception cycles from 25 reports and 8 reports found that the difference in the mean endometrial thickness of conception and non-conception cycles was statistically significant, while 17 reports found no significant difference. They concluded that results from various trials are conflicting and that insufficient data exist describing a linear correlation between endometrial thickness and the probability of conception. There is not enough data to demonstrate if a linear relationship exists between endometrial thickness and the probability of pregnancy.¹⁶

In vivo, most viable tissues, including the endometrium, need adequate blood supply with angiogenesis for their development and proliferation. Therefore, in the endometrium and the uterus, proper angiogenesis is considered essential for implantation.

4 METHODOLOGY

4.1 Study design and setting

This was a hospital based prospective descriptive study carried out in the Infertility Clinic of the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology (GOPD), Tribhuwan University Teaching Hospital (TUTH), Kathmandu.

4.2 Study period

The study was conducted over a period of one year starting from 1st Jestha 2072 to 1st Jestha 2073 (15th April 2015 to 14th April 2016).

4.3 Study population

The study population comprised of all women attending Infertility Clinic of TU Teaching Hospital for subfertility work up.

4.4 Sample size

All the women attending infertility clinic of TU Teaching Hospital.

Total number of patients attending Infertility Clinic in 2071 BS was 1007.

4.5 Inclusion criteria

- Women attending infertility clinic of TUTH with primary or secondary subfertility, regardless of age and parity.

4.6 Exclusion criteria

- Women whose male partners have abnormal semen analysis
- Women with tubal subfertility (bilateral tubal block)
- Women with follicle size <16mm and >22mm on follicular monitoring
- Women who failed to develop adequate sized follicle till day 20 of the cycle
- Women with antral follicular count <7
- Women with ovarian cyst
- Women with endometrial polyp
- Women with history of pelvic tuberculosis
- Women with thyroid dysfunction
- Women with hyperprolactinemia
- Women who received chemotherapy
- Women who received radiotherapy
- Women who were lost to follow up
- Women who were not willing to consent for the study

4.7 Data Collection Procedure

4.7.1 Ethical Consideration

Ethical clearance for the study was taken from the institutional review board of Institute of Medicine (IOM), TUTH. All women were explained in detail about the study and procedure involved. Only those women who consented to participate were included in the study after obtaining written consent. Confidentiality of all the information was maintained.

4.7.2 Preliminaries

A pretest was conducted in 10 women prior to starting the study to find out the practical difficulties that might be encountered in the process of study. The modifications were made according to the findings.

4.7.3 Enrollment in the study

The data collection was done during OPD days. All the couples attending the infertility clinic of TUTH were worked up taking detail history with examination and performing necessary investigations according to the clinic protocol. Women who fulfilled the inclusion criteria and agreed to enroll in the study were chosen for the study.

Selected women were counseled about subfertility, risk factors, investigations and management. They were also explained about the study, the procedure involved and written consent was obtained.

4.7.4 History, Examination, Filling of questionnaire

A detailed history was taken including socio- demographic profile, occupation, menstrual history, obstetric history, history of previous subfertility investigations treatment, medical history and history pertaining to presence of risk factors associated with subfertility. The information was recorded in structured questionnaire.

Women with history of pelvic tuberculosis, pelvic irradiation, and chemotherapy were excluded.

4.7.5 Selection of the case

Detail history of all the couples i.e. 1130 women who attended Infertility Clinic of TUTH were taken and examined and all baseline investigations including complete blood count, random blood sugar, blood grouping along with male partner's seminal analysis was done.

Women whose male partner semen analysis showed WHO defined oligospermia or azoospermia or asthenospermia were excluded from the study.

After excluding male factor of infertility, women were followed on day 2 or 3 of menstruation and hormone profile including FSH, LH, Estradiol, Progesterone, Prolactin and Thyroid function test were sent.

If women presented on day 2 to 3 of cycle, all the baseline investigations and hormone profile were sent on the same day.

Women with hypothyroidism, hyperthyroidism, hyperprolactinoma, hypergonadotropic hypogonadism, hypogonadotropic hypogonadism were excluded from study population.

Women were called on day 5 of the cycle to see complete shedding of the endometrium, antral follicle count was done and other pathologies like ovarian cyst, endometrial polyp, submucous fibroid, uterine structural anomaly were ruled out. Women with AFC less than 7 and above mentioned pathologies were excluded from the study.

The transvaginal sonogram model using B mode scan with volume probe of 7.5 megahertz was used by single operator.

Hysterosalpingogram was done in between day 6 to day 10 of cycle and women with bilateral tubal block, uterine structural anomaly were excluded from the study.

Women without any of above mentioned abnormalities and who agreed to enroll in the study were given low dose combined oral contraceptive pills (levonorgestrel 0.15mg, ethinylestradiol 0.03mg) once daily for 21 days from day 1 of next cycle.

After one cycle of low dose combined OCP following withdrawal bleed, women were prescribed 50 mg clomiphene citrate once daily for 5 days from day 2 to day 6 of cycle.

Follicular monitoring was done from 9th day onwards and those who had adequate size follicle (16-22 mm), endometrial vascularity was evaluated according to Applebaum's criteria along with endometrial thickness. Endometrial color Doppler sonography (Aloka 1700, Japan, 7.5 MHZ probe) was performed to obtain endometrial parameters till the development of adequate sized follicle (≥ 16 mm to

<22mm) or till day 20 of cycle who failed to develop adequate sized follicle. The women who failed to develop adequate size follicle were excluded from the study.

Color mapping of endometrial vascularity, according to the degree of penetration into the endometrium and endometrial thickness were classified as follows:

Zone I (absent): when only surrounding myometrial vessels are seen without reaching the endometrium.

Zone II (sub-endometrial): color signals reach the hyperechogenic outer layer of the endometrium

Zone III (outer hyperechogenic Zone): when color mapping occupies the outer half of the endometrial hypoechogenic thickness

Zone IV (inner hypoechogenic Zone): vessels reach the endometrial cavity invading the entire endometrial thickness and therefore penetrate all layers of endometrium.

Endometrial thickness was measured in longitudinal plane at the site of maximal thickness in full view of uterus and grouped into <6mm, 6-14mm, >14mm.

Intramuscular beta-hCG 5000 IU was given once follicle reached adequate size and LH surge was confirmed by commercially available LH surge kit by the women themselves after 12 hours of injection every 12 hours till test was positive for next 48 hours following beta-hCG injection. The test was regarded as positive if two solid lines were seen and presumed that ovulation would occur. If LH surge test remained negative even after 48 hours of beta-hCG injection then those women were excluded from the study.

Those who tested positive were considered as a case and were subjected to intrauterine insemination (IUI) (prepared by swim up technique) after 36 hours. Women who wanted natural conception were asked to have coitus during that period.

The pregnancy was confirmed by urine beta-hCG test 21 days after LH surge test using commercially available urine pregnancy kit which showed two solid lines and those who tested positive were confirmed by transvaginal sonogram after three to four weeks.

4.8 Data management and analysis

The data collected were entered in the master chart. Analysis was done using SPSS version 22. Results are presented in figures and tables and presented in numbers and percentages. Chi square test was applied where applicable to find out statistical significance. **The p-value <0.05 was regarded as statistically significant.** Midterm analysis was done and presented.

5 RESULTS

During the study period, 1130 couples attended the Infertility Clinic for subfertility work up. Among those women who fulfilled the inclusion criteria and gave consent were enrolled in the study. 1049 women were excluded from the study while 81 women who were LH surge positive were included in the study and taken for the statistical calculation.

Among 81 women, 21 (25.92%) were UPT positive while 60 (74.08%) tested negative for pregnancy.

The results are presented under the following headings:

Characteristics of women

Correlation of Endometrial thickness with Pregnancy

Correlation of Endometrial vascularity with Pregnancy

Figure 7: Flow chart showing distribution of subfertile couples attending infertility clinic

The flow chart shows the distribution of the women attending subfertility clinic. Total 1130 couples attended subfertility clinic for the work up. Among these women 1049 were excluded. 237 women were excluded due to male factor of subfertility, 158 women were excluded due to endocrinological factor, 49 women were excluded due to tubal factor of subfertility, 109 women were excluded due to ovarian factor, 21 women were excluded due to uterine factor and 19 women were LH surge negative hence

excluded. In ovarian factor exclusion, 27 women failed to develop adequate sized follicle while other 82 women were excluded due to ovarian cyst, endometriosis, etc.

456 women were lost to follow up.

5.1 Characteristics of Women

5.1.1 Type of Subfertility

Figure 8: Distribution of women by type of subfertility

Most of the women belonged to primary subfertility group i.e. 71% while remaining 29% belonged to secondary subfertility group.

5.1.2 Age distribution

Figure 9: Distribution of women by age (in years)

Most of the women were between the age group 26-30 years accounting for 46.9% of study population. Those below 20 years were 1.2% and above 35 years were 4.9%. The mean age was 25.83 ± 4.34 years with minimum 19 years and maximum 42 years.

5.1.3 Occupation

Figure 10: Distribution by occupation of women

Maximum women i.e. 63% were homemaker. Twenty one women i.e. 26% were service holder and remaining 11% were self-employed.

5.1.4 Level of Education

Figure 11: Distribution of women by level of education

Of the study population most women i.e. 29.6% belonged to higher secondary education level while there were only five women i.e. 6.2% with primary level education.

5.1.5 Body Mass Index (BMI)

Figure 12: Distribution of women by body mass index

Fifty women (61.9%) were of normal BMI, 29.6% were overweight and 4.9% were obese. 2.4% had BMI less than 18.5 kg/m². The mean BMI was 23.21± 3.61 kg/m² with minimum of 16 kg/m² and maximum of 39.8 kg/m².

5.1.6 Endometrial Vasculature

Figure 13: Distribution of women by zone of endometrial vascularity

Thirty eight women accounting for 4% of study population had zone III endometrial vascularity followed by zone II (28.3%) and zone IV (21%). There were only three women with zone I endometrial vascularity.

5.1.7 Endometrial Thickness

Figure 14: Distribution of women by endometrial thickness (in mm)

Most of the women i.e. 82.72% had endometrial thickness of 6 to 14 mm. Fourteen women had thickness <6 mm and no woman had thickness more than 14 mm.

5.1.8 Mean Endometrial Thickness in different Age group

Age in Years	Endometrial Thickness in mm
<20	7.50mm
20-25	7.99mm
26-30	7.96mm
31-35	7.94mm
>35	6.7mm

Table 1: Mean endometrial thickness in women of different age group

Women in all the age group had mean endometrial thickness of approximately 7.9mm with thickest being 7.99mm in 20 to 25 age group and thinnest being 6.7mm in >35 age group.

Mean endometrial thickness was 7.8mm in women who became pregnant in the study population.

5.2 IUI vs Natural Conception

Figure 15: Distribution of implantation by IUI and natural conception

Twelve women i.e. 57% became pregnant after IUI while 43% became pregnant by natural conception.

5.2.1 Endometrial Vascularity in Women who became Pregnant by IUI vs Natural Conception

Endometrial Vascularity	IUI	Natural Conception
Zone I	0	0
Zone II	3	1
Zone III	6	8
Zone IV	3	0
Total	12	9

Table 2: Distribution of women who conceived by IUI or natural means according to different zones of endometrial vascularity

12 women conceived by means of IUI while 9 women conceived naturally and among them majority of women had zone III endometrial vascularity. Three women with zone II endometrial vascularity conceived in IUI group while only one women conceived naturally.

5.3 Correlation of type of Subfertility with implantation

Category	Type of subfertility		Total
	Primary Subfertility	Secondary Subfertility	
Pregnant	14	7	21
Non Pregnant	44	16	60
Total	58	23	81

Table 3: Distribution of women by type of subfertility in pregnant and non pregnant group

Majority of the women belonged to primary subfertility group i.e. 67% while remaining 33% belonged to secondary subfertility group.

The correlation between type of subfertility and pregnancy is not statistically significant as p-value is not <0.05 (p-value: 0.559812).

5.4 Correlation of Implantation with Age

Category	Age in Years					Total
	<20	20-25	26-30	31-35	>35	
Pregnant	0	6	13	1	1	21
Non Pregnant	1	18	25	13	3	60
Total	1	24	38	14	4	81

Table 4: Distribution of women by age (in years) in pregnant and non pregnant group

Most of the women were between the age group 26-30 years in both groups of study population. There was no women below 20 years who became pregnant. There was one women of 42 years who became pregnant. The mean age group was 27 years in both group of women. The correlation between age and pregnancy was not statistically significant as p-value was not <0.05 (p-value: 0.367862).

5.5 Correlation of Implantation with Body Mass Index

Category	BMI (kg/m ²)					Total
	<18.5	≥18.5 - <25	≥25 - <30	≥30 - <35	≥35	
Pregnant	1	14	5	1	0	21
Non Pregnant	1	36	19	3	1	60
Total	2	50	24	4	1	81

Table 5: Distribution of women by body mass index in pregnant and non pregnant group

Maximum number of women had normal BMI in both pregnant and non-pregnant group of study population. One woman had BMI less than 18.5 kg/m² in the study population who became pregnant.

The correlation between pregnancy and study population was not statistically significant as p-value was not <0.05 (p-value: 0.845677).

5.6 Correlation of Implantation and Endometrial Thickness

Figure 16: Comparison of endometrial thickness between pregnant and non pregnant women

Sixty eight women in the study population i.e. 84% had endometrial thickness between 6-14 mm and most of the implantation i.e. 95.3% were seen in the same group.

In <6 mm endometrial thickness group 15.3% of women became pregnant while in 6-14mm endometrial thickness group 27.9% of women became pregnant.

Endometrial Thickness and Pregnancy

Category	Endometrial Thickness		Total
	<6mm	6-14mm	
Pregnant	1	20	21
Non Pregnant	12	48	60
Total	13	68	81

Table 6: Distribution of women comparing endometrial thickness in pregnant and non pregnant women

According to the Chi square test p value correlating pregnancy and endometrial thickness was 0.10565. As p value is not <0.05 the correlation is not significant.

5.7 Correlation of Implantation and Zone of Endometrial Vascularity

Figure 17: Distribution women comparing implantation in different zone of endometrial vascularity

Thirty eight women (47%) had zone III vascularity and maximum number of implantation was seen in this group accounting for 67% of implantation in study population. Zone I endometrial vascularity had no implantation which accounted for only 3.7% of study population.

Women with zone III vascularity had 36.8% implantation while zone I had no implantation. Zone IV had 17.6% implantation while zone II had 17.3% implantation.

Endometrial vascularity and Pregnancy

Category	Endometrial vascularity				Total
	Zone I	Zone II	Zone III	Zone IV	
Pregnant	0	4	14	3	21
Non-pregnant	3	19	24	14	60
Total	3	23	38	17	81

Table 7: Distribution of women comparing endometrial vascularity in pregnant and non-pregnant women

According to the Chi square test p value correlating pregnancy and endometrial vascularity was 0.180263. As p value is not <0.05 the correlation is not significant.

5.8 Endometrial vascularity, Endometrial thickness and Implantation

Endometrial vascularity	No. of Women	Endometrial thickness and Implantation			
		<6mm	Implantation	6-14mm	Implantation
Zone I	3	0	0	3	0
Zone II	23	5	0	18	4
Zone III	38	6	0	32	14
Zone IV	17	2	1	15	2

Table 8: Distribution of women comparing endometrial vascularity, endometrial thickness with implantation

According to the Pearson Correlation Coefficient as the value of correlation coefficient i.e. $r = -0.1789$ which is greater than -1 so there is low degree of negative correlation between endometrial thickness and endometrial vascularity in pregnant women in this study population.

6 DISCUSSION

Several studies have presented several parameters and assessment techniques to assess the implantation potential of human endometrium. Many studies have been conducted to evaluate the role of various ultrasound parameters in predicting pregnancy.^{45, 46, 47}

This study is type of its own as all reported studies were done in stimulated cycles for invitro fertilization. In the present study, the mean age of the study group was 27 years which is considered a young population and the mean age of the women in the pregnant group was 27 years as well.

Some researchers have reported that endometrial blood flow is considered more important than other sonographic indices such as pattern and thickness of endometrium.⁴⁸ For example, Chien et al have found a positive correlation between vascular penetration into the endometrium and occurrence of pregnancy while this study has shown the correlation to be not significant. On the other hand Zaidi et al measured sub-endometrial blood flow and intraendometrial vascularization on the day of hCG injection among 96 patients undergoing IVF cycles. In 8.3% of non-pregnant patients, subendometrial color flow and intraendometrial vascularization were not detected. This absence of blood flow was associated with failure of implantation like the present study where there were 3 women with zone I and there was no conception among them. These patients were devoid of sub-endometrial color flow and intra-endometrial vascularization. Although the incidence of pregnancy increased with penetration of vessels into the superficial layers of endometrium difference between the layers was not statistically significant.⁴⁸ In this study, most of the patient belonged to zone III endometrial vascularity and most of the implantation i.e. 67% occurred in the same zone followed by zone IV (21%) and zone II (19%) respectively. Considering the

negative correlation between vascular penetration and pregnancy occurrence, this present study was in accordance with the above-mentioned studies.

Comparing vascular pattern revealed that in 4 patients endometrial vessels were absent in zone I, in 43.8% vessels were extended to zone II and in a similar number (32 patients) this extension was up to the middle of the endometrium (zone III). In only 6.8% were the vessels extended up to the interface of the two endometrial layers (zone IV). In our study, 3.7% of the women belonged to zone I, 28.3% belonged to zone II and 47% women belonged to zone III. There were 21% women in zone IV. Vasculature of the endometrium was not statistically different among the two groups in subfertile women with and without implantation as in this study.

Nagori et al have found that endometrial vasculature in zone III and IV are good predictor for pregnancy outcome.

Endometrial thickness ranged from 3.2 to 14 millimeters with mean thickness of 7.9 mm while it was 8 to 25mm in study done by Firzooeh et al. No consensus has been reached with regard to the minimum endometrial thickness required for successful pregnancy. Some studies have shown that pregnancies did not occur when the endometrial thickness was less than 7 mm however, other studies found that a minimum endometrial thickness of 6 mm is acceptable for implantation. Interestingly, Sundström reported a successful pregnancy with an endometrial thickness as little as 4 mm. In our study, the thinnest endometrial lining for successful pregnancy was 5.8 mm and maximum number of conceptions occurred when the thickness was 8–10 mm and the mean endometrial thickness was 7.9mm. With increasing endometrial thickness (≥ 14 mm), no pregnancy was observed in our study and only one woman had endometrial thickness of 14mm.

Also there were lots of studies about measurement of endometrial thickness in prediction of implantation rate. Ultrasonography has been used to relate treatment outcome to both endometrial thickness and morphology of the endometrium in artificial reproductive techniques. Considerable evidences show that endometrial thickness of 9mm or more is related with higher pregnancy rates. In a recent study, EMT of 9-14 mm measured on the day of progesterone supplementation was associated with higher implantation and pregnancy rates compared with an EMT of 7–8 mm by Bassil et al. However, Bassil determined that there were no significant differences in EMT, width, length, growth and pattern in conception compared to non-conception cycles. The endometrial growth and its pattern transformation during the stimulation did not influence the pregnancy outcome. Results of our present study were similar to those of Bassil's study as p value was not significant.

In our study, the overall clinical pregnancy rate was 25.92%. We observed a higher pregnancy rate when the blood flow to the endometrium was in Zone III (67%) compared to other zones. In a prospective study, Wang et al, studied the endometrial thickness, echo pattern and blood flow on transvaginal sonography in 182 women, eight hours prior to hCG injection. They observed a higher clinical pregnancy rate and implantation rate in women with detectable blood flow. Ng et al, observed a lower vascularity in the endometrial and sub-endometrial region by Doppler in patients who had low-volume endometrium as compared to those with thin endometrium. Several studies have suggested that a premature secretory endometrial pattern is introduced by the advanced progesterone rise, and this premature conversion has an adverse effect on pregnancy rates. The reason that no triple lined endometrial pattern was observed prior to ovulation is not known and cannot be explained by higher progesterone levels.

The coexistence of a thinner endometrium in association with no triple line pattern reflects a diminished endometrial responsiveness to ovarian hormones and poor receptivity of the endometrium, leading to a low clinical pregnancy rate and poor clinical outcome.⁵⁴

One limitation of our study is that the number of subjects in the study population was too small to make a definitive statement. Perifollicular vascularity, number of adequate size follicles were not correlated as well.

Investigators like Coulam et al demonstrated that all the pregnancies occurred in women with Grade III and IV endometrium. Our findings are consistent with these of Coulam et al as most of implantation has been seen in the zone III endometrial vascularity.

Thus, the predictive value of endometrial vascularity for treatment outcome is still undecided although three of four studies found that better endometrial blood flow was associated with a higher pregnancy rate.

It appears that the vascularity of endometrial and subendometrial layers measured by Doppler ultrasound was not a good predictor of pregnancy during stimulated IVF and FET cycles if it was measured at one time point only.⁵⁵ The results are not contradictory to those studies that specifically examined perfusion within the human endometrium during the menstrual cycle. Fraser et al determined endometrial blood flow through the menstrual cycle with the use of the clearance of radiolabelled xenon-133 following its instillation into the uterine cavity. There was a significant elevation in the middle-to-late follicular phase, followed by a substantial fall and a secondary slow luteal phase rise that was maintained until the onset of menstruation. More recently, Raine-Fenning et al showed that endometrial and subendometrial vascularity by 3D ultrasound

increased during the proliferative phase, peaking around 3 days prior to ovulation before decreasing to a nadir 5 days post-ovulation.

Raine-Fenning et al further proposed that the degree of change in endometrial perfusion from the late follicular phase through to the early luteal phase was a more important determinant of endometrial receptivity. Hypoxia in the endometrium may play a beneficial role for implantation as the expression of vascular endothelial growth factor is up-regulated by hypoxia⁵⁷, and relatively low oxygen tension was present around the blastocyst during the time of implantation⁵⁸. To confirm or refute this hypothesis, further longitudinal studies on the endometrial and subendometrial vascularity should be performed in the late follicular and early luteal phases.

Chien et al. documented an endometrial–subendometrial blood flow distribution pattern assessed by transvaginal color Doppler before embryo transfer to be correlated with the implantation and pregnancy rate of IVF treatment. Maugey-Laulom et al. concluded that the presence of sub- and intra-endometrial vascularity on the day of ET seemed to be mandatory for obtaining an ongoing pregnancy.

Contradictory to these results, some authors stated that measuring the vascular indices was not helpful in predicting the success rate of fresh-cycle IVF.⁵⁹ Yuval et al. reported that the differences between pregnant and non-pregnant patients was not statistically significant in any of the parameters, such as endometrial color Doppler vascularity and EMT. Schild et al. documented neither Doppler sonography of the spiral or uterine arteries nor measurement of the EMT that allowed a reliable prediction of subsequent IVF outcome. Salle et al. also reported that individual ultrasonographic and Doppler parameters do not have sufficient accuracy to predict uterine receptivity. As mentioned above, there were some controversies about the correlations between measurement of

vascular indices and prediction of successful pregnancy. This conflicting data might be related to the variability of each study design (for example, the measurement timing of blood flow indices were different among studies) which could affect the pregnancy outcome.

Also there were lots of studies about measurement of EMT in prediction of implantation rate. Ultrasonography has been used to relate pregnancy out to both EMT and morphology at the time of embryo transfer. In our study we studied endometrial thickness and the result in successful pregnancy has not been significant.

7 SUMMARY

Majority of the women i.e. 46.9% in the study belonged to the age group of 26 to 30 years. The mean age was 27 years while the mean age in women who became pregnant was 24 years.

Maximum number of women belonged to primary subfertility group i.e. 71% in the study population. 67% of women who became pregnant had primary subfertility and remaining 33% had secondary subfertility.

63% of the women in the study population were homemakers, 26% were service holder and 11% were self-employed. 62% were homemaker, 33% were service holder and 5% were self-employed in women who became pregnant.

Majority of the women in the study population i.e. 61% had normal body mass index and Sixty six percent of women who became pregnant had normal BMI. The mean BMI was $23.21 \pm 3.61 \text{ kg/m}^2$.

The mean endometrial thickness in the study population was 7.9mm while it was 7.8mm in women who became pregnant. The thickest endometrial thickness was 7.99mm in 20 to 25 years age group.

Sixty eight women in the study population i.e. 84% had endometrial thickness between 6-14 mm and most of the implantation i.e. 95.3% were seen in the same group. In <6 mm endometrial thickness group 15.3% of women became pregnant while in 6-14mm endometrial thickness group 27.9% of women became pregnant.

Thirty eight women (47%) had zone III vascularity and maximum number of implantation was seen in this zone accounting for 67% of implantation. Women with

zone III vascularity had 36.8% implantation while zone I had no implantation which accounted for 3.7% of study population. Zone IV had 17.6% implantation while zone II had 17.3% implantation.

The correlation between endometrial thickness and pregnancy was not statistically significant.

The correlation between endometrial thickness and pregnancy was not statistically significant.

The correlation between endometrial thickness, endometrial vascularity and pregnancy showed low degree of negative correlation in this study population.

8 CONCLUSION

The correlation between endometrial vascularity and pregnancy was not statistically not significant in the study population as p value was not <0.05 .

The correlation between endometrial thickness and pregnancy was not statistically not significant in the study population as p value was not <0.05 .

9 LIMITATIONS OF STUDY

The study sample was small as many patient was lost to follow up.

The duration of study was short.

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ANNEXE 1

dGh'/Lgdf

Gfd:sf/ Û d /]lh8]G6 lrlsT;s 8f hLgf jflgof o; lqe'jg ljZj ljBfno lrlsT;f zf:q cWoog ;+:yfgdf “CORRELAATION OF ENDOMETRIAL VASCULARITY AND CONCEPTION AMONG WOMEN WITH SUBFERTILITY” ljifodf cg';Gwfg ul//x]sf] 5' . t'kfO{ xfd]f] cg';Gwfgsf] nflu 5flgg' ePsf]df awfO{ 5 . o; cg';Gwfgsf] s]ddf t'kfO{sf] :jf:Yodf uDeL/ k|lts'n c;/ kg]{ 5}g . o; cg';Gwfgn] eljiodf o; /f]usf] pkrf/ ;DjGwL / pQm k4ltsf] kmfObf a]kmfObf?sf] 7f]; k|df0fx? h'6fpg ;xof]u ug]{ 5 . t;y{ d tkfO{ / cleefjsnfO{ o; cg';Gwfgdf ;xefuL eO{ ;xof]u ul/lbg' x'g xflb{s cg'/f]w ub{5' .

tkfO{sf] ;Dk'0f{ ljj/0fx? tkfO{n} rfx]sf] afx]s uf]Ko g} /flvg] 5 . o;df tkfO{ cfkm'n] grfx]sf] s'g}klg a]nfdcf cf^gf] ;xeflutf lkmtf{ lng klg ;Sg' x'g]5 . tkfO{sf] s'g} k|Zg 5 eg] d v'zL ;fy pQ/ lbg]5' .

olb tkfO{ o; cg';Gwfgdf ;+nUg x'g rfxg'x'G5 eg] s[kof cf^gf] k"0f{ dGh'/Lsf] lnltv ?kdf x:tflf/ ul/lbgx'g cg'/f]w ub{5' .

dGh'/L lbg]sf] gfd

y/ :

gftf :

x:tflf/:

bfof'	afof'

lrlsT;ssf] gfd y/ :

x:tflf/:

ANNEXE 2

PORFORMA

PATIENT'S IDENTIFICATION

Form No:

Name:

Age:

Address:

- Permanent:
- Temporary:

Ethnicity:

Religion:

Contact no:

Socio economic status:

Education:

- Wife
- Husband

Occupation:

- Wife
- Husband

MENSTRUAL HISTORY

- Menarche (yrs):
- Cycle: Regular/Irregular
- LMP:

OBSTETRIC HISTORY

- Age at marriage
- Married for (yrs)
- Trying to conceive for (yrs)
- Parity index Gravida... Para... Living... Abortion...

CONTRACEPTION HISTORY

- Yes/no
- If yes, method used.....duration

HISTORY OF PAST ILLNESS

- Past medical history
 - Mumps, Tuberculosis, Diabetes, Hypertension
 - Previous treatment history for subfertility
- Past surgical history

FAMILY HISTORY

PERSONAL HISTORY

- Smoker/non smoker
- Alcohol abuse: Yes/No
- Vegetarian/Non vegetarian
- Sleep/Appetite
- Bowel/Bladder

DRUG HISTORY

- H/o allergy if present specify

SEXUAL HISTORY

- Living together or not
- If yes no. of years together
- Frequency of coitus per week
- Any difficulty during the coitus
- Dyspareunia
- Decreased sexual desire
- Premature ejaculation

PHYSICAL EXAMINATION

Height:

Weight:

Pallor:

Lymphadenopathy:

Hirsutism:

Icterus:

Edema:

VITALS

Temperature:

Pulse:

BP:

Thyroid

Breast

SYSTEMIC EXAMINATION

Chest

CVS

CNS

Per Abdomen

Per Speculum Examination

Bimanual Examination

INVESTIGATIONS

Hemoglobin:

ESR:

Blood group:

TC/DC:

VDRL, HIV, HbSAg:

RBS:

Hysterosalpigogram:

Chest Xray (if required):

Mantoux test (if required):

Hormonal Assay:

FSH

LH

Estrogen

Progesterone

Prolactin

Testosterone

TFT

Others

Seminogram (for male partner)

TRANSVAGINAL SONOGRAPHY

Date	Day of cycle	No. and size of follicle		Endometrial vascularity	Endometrial thickness
		Right ovary	Left ovary		

OVULATION AND INDUCTION

Drugs/Procedures	Date
Clomiphene	
Beta-hCG	
Intra Uterine Insemination (IUI)	
Others	

ANNEXE 3

APPROVAL LETTER FROM IRB

त्रिभुवन विश्वविद्यालय
चिकित्सा शास्त्र अध्ययन संस्थान
डीनको कार्यालय, महाराजगंज
पो.ब.नं: १५२४, काठमाडौं, नेपाल।
फोन नं. ४४१०९११, ४४१२०४०, ४४१३२२९, ४४१८१८७

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मिति / Date:- 14 June, 2016

Dr. Jeena Baniya
MD Resident
Department of Obstetrics & Gynecology
Maharajgunj Medical Campus
Maharajgunj

Re: Approval of Research Proposal: Correlation of endometrial vascularity and conception among subfertile women.

Dear, Dr. Baniya,
Thank you for the submission of your thesis proposal entitled "**Correlation of endometrial vascularity and conception among subfertile women**" in the meeting of Institutional Review Board, Institute of Medicine, Tribhuvan University on 13 May, 2015.
I am pleased to inform you that the above mentioned research proposal has been approved by Institutional Review Board, Institute of Medicine on 14 June, 2016.
As per IRB rules and regulations the investigator has to strictly follow the protocol stipulated in the proposal. Any change in objective, problem statement, research questions or hypothesis, methodology, implementation procedure, data management and budget may be made so and implemented after prior approval from this Research Department and IRB. Thus, it is compulsory to submit the detail of such changes intended or desired with justifications prior to actual change in the protocol.
You are also requested to follow the ethical guideline of IRB, Institute of Medicine.
After completion of your study you must submit a copy of thesis to Research Department.
If you have any further queries, please do not hesitate to contact us.

Prof. Dr. Mohan Raj Sharma
Chairman
Institutional Review Board

HOD
Department of Obstetrics & Gynecology
Maharajgunj Medical Campus
Maharajgunj.

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